

CDA NEWSLETTER

A PUBLICATION OF CENTRE FOR DRYLAND AGRICULTURE, BAYERO UNIVERSITY, KANO, NIGERIA

Volume 7 No.2

APRIL - JUNE 2019

ISSN: 2350-210X

BUK Selected to Host PASET PhD Programmes

...One of the Top 7 Winning African Universities Out of 144

ALSO INSIDE

- DG ICRISAT Visits BUK, Promises More Collaborative Opportunities
- CDA Organizes Orientation for New Students
- BUK's CDA Now Member Regional Consortium of Agricultural ACEs

CENTRE FOR DRYLAND AGRICULTURE

Bayero University, Kano – Nigeria

... an Africa Centre of Excellence in Dryland Agriculture

VISION

Resilient and Prosperous African Drylands

MISSION

To improve livelihood, resilience and sustainable use of natural resources in African drylands through training and demand-driven research

CORE VALUES

- Good leadership and Inclusiveness
- Passion and Teamwork
- Commitment and Sacrifice
- Integrity and Transparency
- Professionalism and Excellence

EDITORIAL TEAM

Editor in Chief

Professor Jibrin M. Jibrin

Deputy Editor in Chief

Professor Amina Mustapha

Sub- Editor

Professor Sanusi Gaya Mohammed

Editor: Nura Garba

Contributing Editors

Dr. Kabir Mustapha

Dr. Aminu Fagge

Dr. Yusuf Garba

Dr. Murtala Badamasi

Dr. Amina L. Mustapha

BUK Selected to Host PASET PhD Programmes

...One of the Top 7 Winning African Universities Out of 144

Bayero University has been selected to serve as one of the host universities for Partnership for Skills in Applied Sciences, Engineering and Technology (PASET), a Pan African Regional Scholarship and Innovation Fund (RSIF) for PhD programmes.

On Thursday, 9th May, 2019, the Regional Scholarship and Innovation Fund (RSIF) of PASET sent a congratulatory letter to the Vice Chancellor, Professor Muhammad Yahuza Bello on the selection of BUK as one of the institutions to host its PhD programmes.

Part of the letter reads: "The selection process has been highly competitive and rigorous: Out of 144 applications received, 80 applications were found to be compliant/eligible and were each reviewed by three independent external reviewers. Sixteen doctoral programmes were shortlisted visited for on-site validation that focused on the proposal and staff capacity. The RSIF Independent Evaluation Committee at its meeting of 24th April, 2019 discussed the results of the evaluation and recommended seven universities to be considered as PASET African Host Universities."

According to the letter signed by RSIF-RSU Manager, Dr. Moses Osiru, "we are pleased to inform you that following a competitive process, Bayero

University and in particular, the PhD Programme in Natural Resource Management and Climate Change has been selected by the Executive Board of PASET as one of seven African Universities to host PASET doctoral scholars and RSIF research and innovation activities."

The PASET's Validation Team had on 18th April, 2019 visited Bayero University, Kano and evaluated the Centre for Dryland Agriculture's (CDA) supported PhD programmes in Natural Resource Management and Climate Change (NRM&CC), hosted in the Department of Geography. During the visit, the team interacted with staff and inspected facilities of the Centre.

The PASET is an initiative by African governments to address fundamental gaps in skills and knowledge necessary for long term, sustained economic growth in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). It established Regional Scholarship and Innovation Fund (RSIF) to contribute towards the training of a critical mass of PhD and post-doctoral candidates, and support research and innovation in some priority thematic areas: ICTs, including big data and artificial intelligence; food security and agribusiness; minerals, mining and materials engineering renewable energy and climate change.

The PASET plans to train ten thousand PhDs in different areas within a period of 10 years.

DG ICRISAT Visits BUK, Promises More Collaborative Opportunities

The Director-General of the International Crops Research Institute for the Semi-Arid Tropics (ICRISAT), Dr Peter Carberry, visited Bayero University, Kano on Thursday, 25th April, 2019 and promised that the two institutions would explore more opportunities for collaboration.

ICRISAT is an international organization which conducts agricultural research on cereals and legumes for rural development, headquartered in Patancheru (Hyderabad, India) with several regional centres around the world including one in Kano

It is one of the strongest international partners of the Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) of Bayero University, Kano.

The ICRISAT DG, who paid a courtesy call on the Vice Chancellor, Professor Muhammad Yahuza Bello, praised the institute's fruitful partnership with Bayero University and vowed to explore other avenues to further strengthen the collaboration. He said he was happy with the way the collaboration with the CDA was

yielding fruitful results, especially in the areas of agricultural research and capacity building of personnel.

The Vice Chancellor, who was represented by the Deputy Vice Chancellor (Academics) Professor Adamu Idris Tanko, said ICRISAT is one of the strong partners the CDA has, noting that the University allocated a 15-hectare research field to ICRISAT as a gesture to appreciate the partnership. He called on the ICRISAT DG to explore

additional collaborative opportunities that would benefit both ICRISAT and BUK.

While at the CDA, Dr. Carberry visited the Centre's farm and laboratories, interacted with the staff, and inspected the ICRISAT's research field. He commended the University Management for their support in allocating the research field to ICRISAT.

Dr. Carberry assured the Centre of ICRISAT's willingness to support research and teaching activities around GIS and Remote Sensing, Agricultural and Environmental Systems modeling to help the Centre towards achieving its goals. Furthermore, the DG reiterated the commitment of ICRISAT to assist in training and capacity development of CDA staff and students.

In his earlier remarks, the Director, CDA, Professor Jibrin M. Jibrin, welcomed the ICRISAT DG and expressed optimism that the Centre was living up to the expectation of the World Bank and would continue to strengthen the partnership between the two institutions.

CDA Competitively Chosen for PASET's PhD Programmes Validation - Dr. Osiru

Bayero University's Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) was competitively chosen for validation of the Partnership for Skills in Applied Sciences, Engineering and Technology (PASET's) Pan African Regional Scholarship and Innovation Fund (RSIF) PhD programmes, said a validation team leader, Dr Moses Osiru, while briefing the Vice Chancellor, Professor Muhammad Yahuza Bello of the team's mission in BUK on 18th April, 2019.

Dr. Osiru, who is the Manager, RSIF Regional Coordination Unit, informed the Vice Chancellor that Centre for Dryland Agriculture's supported PhD programmes in Natural Resource Management and Climate Change had passed through rigorous technical evaluation process involving review by three independent technical reviewers. He said their visit was to make an onsite validation. "If Bayero University scales through this validation, it will be selected as one of the universities to host PASET PhD programmes," he assured.

Dr Osiru added that BUK's proposal was one of the 15 proposals selected for on-site evaluation. He said 144 proposals were received, 80 qualified for desk review, out of which the best 3 in each of the 5 thematic areas of PASET were selected for on-site evaluation.

The Vice Chancellor, Professor Muhammad Yahuza Bello, who was represented by the Deputy Vice Chancellor, Administration, Professor Haruna Wakili, welcomed the PASET Team to Bayero University and said the University was indeed happy to be visited for the PASET validation. He said the University has always pursued excellence that is why it was lucky to have two academic Centres of Excellence, CDA and ACEPHAP.

The Team had asked several questions about the University's mission, vision and strategic plan. The Vice Chancellor along with the Director Academic Planning, Professor Bala Sidi Aliyu and Director, CDA, Professor Jibrin M. Jibrin responded to all the questions.

While at the Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA), the Director, Professor Jibrin M. Jibrin briefed the team about the historical background of Bayero University and the evolution of the Centre, which he said started from the humble beginning and metamorphosed to become one of the strategic

DR. MOSES OSIRU

Centre for Dryland Agriculture's supported PhD programmes in Natural Resource Management and Climate Change had passed through rigorous technical evaluation process involving review by three independent technical reviewers

academic Centres of Excellence in Africa with students from across West and Central African countries.

The Team also interacted with staff and students of CDA, Department of Geography and some of the partners of CDA. The Team also visited GIS Laboratory, Molecular Laboratory, CDA Farm and Tissue Culture Laboratory among other facilities.

The Team was highly impressed with the state-of-the-art facilities and the huge investment made in the CDA, as well as the commitment, resilience and the zeal to partner with PASET.

The two independent evaluators who accompanied Dr. Moses Osiru were Tesfa Tegegne of Bahir Dar University, Ethiopia and Professor Kandionra NOBA from University Chakh Anta Diop de Dakar Senegal.

CDA Organizes Orientation for New Students

The Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) has organized orientation for newly admitted students pursuing higher degrees in its supported programmes in various departments of the University. The students comprised of 48 MSc and 13 PhD candidates of which 44 were Nigerians while 17 were regional admitted from over eleven West and Central African countries.

The orientation programme was organized to provide the opportunity for new students to acquaint themselves with the university's culture, rules and regulations, as well as intimate them on the academic tasks ahead of them.

The Director of CDA, Professor Jibrin M. Jibrin welcomed the students and congratulated them having gained admission into one of the best universities in Nigeria.

He informed the students that the Centre has state-of-the-art facilities that can be used to facilitate their research activities, noting that the Centre is ready to support researchers that will address problems outlined in its research thematic areas.

He said four research groups were constituted to come up with key thematic research areas which students can key in to develop their work. He added that any student that develops good proposal can apply for a grant that will support his research.

The Director informed the new students that CDA has been organizing short courses by inviting resource persons from within and outside the country, in order to prepare students to be relevant

and excellent in their various specializations.

Professor Jibrin further explained that the CDA has become truly international with foreign students from many countries and modest state-of-the-art facilities that can be used for cutting-edge research activities.

He said the centre's supported programmes in Natural Resource Management and Climate Change was recently selected to be among the only seven in Africa for Partnership for Skills in Applied Sciences, Engineering and Technology (PASET's) Pan African Regional Scholarship and Innovation Fund (RSIF) PhD programmes in which 144 applications were received and reviewed by the independent bodies.

Also speaking, the Deputy Director, Training, Professor Sanusi Gaya Mohammed gave a brief history of CDA, which started with a humble beginning in 2012 to metamorphose into one of the strategic academic centres of excellence with students from many countries in Africa.

Professor Gaya explained further that the Centre has modest teaching and learning facilities and that it conducts training to both staff and students. He stated that there has been high influx of applications from various parts of the world, adding that centre did not admit 35% of the applicants this year."

Presentations were made on the Use of Library (Faculty of Agriculture Librarian), Internship and Outreach Activities of CDA (Dr. Murtala M. Badamasi), Thematic Research Areas of CDA and Accessing CDA Grant (Dr. K.M. Umar), Campus Life (Dean Student Affairs, Dr Shamsuddeen Umar), as well as Rules and Regulations of PG Studies in BUK (Dr. Yusuf Garba).

CDA has state-of-the-art facilities that can be used to facilitate students' research activities... The Centre is ready to support researchers that will address problems outlined in its research thematic areas.

- Prof. Jibrin M. Jibrin

BUK's CDA Now Member Regional Consortium of Agricultural ACEs

PROF. M.Y. BELLO
Vice-Chancellor, Bayero University, Kano

Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) of Bayero University, Kano is now a member of a consortium for *Agricultural Education and Innovation Frontrunners in West Africa* (CAEIFWA) of the Africa Centres of Excellence (ACEs).

During a workshop for the Agricultural Education Front-runners in West Africa: ACEs Learning Experience of the agricultural ACEs, held at Lome, Togo from 14th – 15th May, 2019, the members agreed to form a consortium to help them work together as a team to address the major challenge of food insecurity in the West African sub-region. A regional approach to higher education through the formation of consortiums such as CAEIFWA will offer a better opportunity to build and sustain excellence in higher education in agriculture for the development of African economies.

The consortium will serve to provide networking opportunities for faculty and students of member ACEs. The undertakings of the consortium are expected to result in well-resourced member ACEs and sustained projects through partnerships with the public and private sector including non-governmental organizations.

CAEIFWA will offer the individual member ACEs the opportunity to network, increase collaborations and unify advocacy efforts. The consortium was established to among other things provide a platform for fund raising for collaborative research towards development of the needed human capacity to aid the fight for food and nutritional security.

It will also provide a network of scientists and researchers working in Agriculture Research for Development; sub-regional collaborative research projects; network of Universities for student and staff exchange; website and a Knowledge Management Hub to serve as a resource in guiding future research agenda, as well as an annual conference on Agriculture and Food and Nutritional Security in West and Central Africa.

The expected outcomes of the activities of CAEIFWA include increased enrolment of regional students in partner institutions, well-resourced ACEs, sustained ACE concept beyond the World Bank phase, increased funds for research and development, funded collaborative sub-regional research projects, database of scientists and researchers in Agriculture Research for Development established and joint publications in peer-review journals.

The consortium was formally established with the vision *Front Runners in Education and Innovation for Food Security in Africa* and mission to *harness resources for gender sensitive regional education and innovation for food security*. This would be attained by harnessing resources for gender sensitive regional education and innovation for food security.

At the end of the meeting, the CDA and other members of the consortium agreed to aggressively raise funds, be committed as member institutions towards realization of its goal, effective partnership and efficient management of resources.

The meeting was attended by Professor J.M. Jibrin (Director/Centre Leader of the CDA), Professor S.G. Mohammed (Deputy Centre Leader/Deputy Director, Training) and Dr. Y. Garba (Project Manager for ACE Impact / Co-ordinator Training).

The consortium will serve to provide networking opportunities for faculty and students of member ACEs. The undertakings of the consortium are expected to result in well-resourced member ACEs and sustained projects through partnerships with the public and private sector including non-governmental organizations.

PASET TEAM INTERACTS WITH CDA PARTNERS

A team of Partnership for Skills in Applied Sciences, Engineering and Technology (PASET) that came for validation of Centre for Dryland Agriculture's supported PhD programmes in Natural Resource Management and Climate Change on Wednesday, 18th April, 2019 interacted with some key partners of the Centre.

The team leader, Dr. Moses Osiru told the partners that the PASET's plan was to train 10,000 PhDs over the next 10 years, but the immediate action is to recruit 100 students between 2019 and 2020, who will be stationed at some specific partner Universities.

Dr. Osiru, who is the Manager, Pan African Regional Scholarship and Innovation Fund (RSIF) of PASET explained that they were now in the process of identifying which universities they are going to station the programmes based on the thematic areas which are: ICTs, including big data and artificial intelligence; food security and agribusiness; minerals, mining and materials engineering; renewable energy and climate change.

"Through the first process, Bayero University was shortlisted to be among the potential universities to host the PASET PhD programmes and now we are here for onsite evaluation. We recognize the importance of partners that's

why we want to interact with you to understand the type of partnership you have with the CDA. Partners can tell you how the University students are being supervised and they will help you to know the University better," he said.

The team leader, who introduced two independent evaluators Tesfa Tegegne of Bahir Dar University, Ethiopia and Professor Kandionra NOBA from University Chakh Anta Diop de Dakar Senegal to the partners, said the Regional Scholarship Innovation Fund (RSIF) has close to \$6m generated from partner countries as each partner country contributes \$2m to the Fund. He

said so far Niger Republic, Burkina Faso and Togo had all partnered and contributed while there was strong commitment from the Nigerian government through the National Universities Commission (NUC) to partner. He said PASET has over \$15m with funding from South Korea and the World Bank.

According to Dr. Alpha Kamara of the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA), his institute and CDA had many research collaborations with several MSc and PhD students being graduated through the partnership. He told the team that CDA has the required infrastructure and state of the art facilities that can accommodate any programme in addition to its competent personnel.

Dr. Kamara added that IITA and CDA had partnered in students' internship programme, remote sensing and Geographical Information System, as well as in projects like TAMASA, STARS and TRIMMING that benefitted both parties.

According to representatives of Nigerian Erosion and Water management Project and NASRDA, Mukhtar Bello and Dr. I.Y Tudun Wada their institutions' partnership with the CDA was fruitful and recommended its capabilities to host PASET PhD programmes.

BUK's 35th Convocation: CDA Graduates 8 PhDs, 26 MSCs from 6 Countries

Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) graduated a total of thirty-four candidates, eight PhDs and twenty-six MSCs under its supported programmes of Livelihood and Natural Resource Management, Range and Livestock Management in Drylands, Crops and Cropping Systems in Drylands and Natural Resource Management and Climate Change.

The PhD and MSc graduands were from Mali, Cameroon, Sudan, Niger Republic, Gambia and Nigeria. They were presented to the Vice Chancellor, Professor Muhammad Yahuza Bello for the conferment of higher degrees at the grand finale of Bayero University's 35th Convocation Ceremony held on Saturday, 15th June, 2019 after being found worthy in character and learning.

The Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) organized a grand reception to celebrate the graduands who had successfully completed their studies on Saturday, 15th June, 2019 at the CDA Conference Hall.

The Director of the Centre, Professor Jibrin M. Jibrin congratulated the graduands for the successful completion of their programmes and urged them to continue to be connected with the Centre even after they return to their respective countries and places,

saying that they would continue to be partners in progress.

The Director called on the graduates especially those that graduated with an MSc in Natural Resource Management and Climate Change to take advantage of Partnership for Skills in Applied Sciences, Engineering and Technology (PASET's) scholarship programmes, which he said CDA's supported PhD programme in NRM&CC had been selected as one of the 7 programmes from 144 applications in Africa.

He informed the graduates that applications for PASET programmes had commenced and each successful candidate stands a chance of getting \$21,000. He assured them that they had the potentials of being admitted into the relevant programmes.

According to Hamdein Mohammed Berima, a Sudanese national and PhD graduand of Range and Livestock Management in Drylands, said he had learnt a lot in terms of analytical methods which assisted him greatly to complete his work. He also benefitted immensely from the CDA' short course trainings, laboratory equipment and other facilities.

According to another PhD graduand of Livelihood and Natural Resource Management, Aly Ahamadou from Mali, said CDA assisted them greatly towards

having an atmosphere conducive for learning and research. He said he would always be proud to be associated with the CDA.

Ahamadou added that he connected many Malian nationals with the centre and many others are willing to apply for CDA supported programmes. He expressed commendation to the staff of CDA for their support throughout their stay in Bayero University Kano.

Dean, Faculty of Agriculture, Deputy Director,

Training, CDA, Professor S.G. Mohammed, Heads of Department of Animal Science, Dr. Nuhu Bello Rano and Agronomy, Dr. S.U. Yahya, all congratulated the graduands and urged them to be good ambassadors of CDA and Bayero University where ever they find themselves in the future.

Among the graduates were CDA staff, Dr. Amina L. Mustapha and Ismail Garba.

The graduands, their programmes and nationality are indicated below:

S/N	Name	Programme	Nationality
1	Aly Ahamadou	PhD in Livelihood and Natural Resource Management	Mali
2	Ndaghu Ndokeu Nathaniel	PhD in Livelihood and Natural Resource Management	Cameroon
3	Muhammad Halliru	PhD in Livelihood and Natural Resource Management	Nigeria
4.	Mahamadou Baba Konate	PhD in Crops and Cropping Systems in the Drylands	Mali
5.	Hamdein Mohammaed Berima Mutwakei	PhD in Range and Livestock Management in Drylands	Sudan
6.	Nourou Ado Alassan	PhD in Range and Livestock Management in Drylands	Niger Republic
7.	Seyni Seybou Abdoul-Aziz	PhD in Natural Resource Management and Climate Change	Niger Republic
8.	Yorombe Dit Yoro Karembe	PhD in Natural Resource Management and Climate Change	Mali
9	Mahmud Mohammed Makki	MSc Livelihood and Natural Resource Management	Nigeria
10	Mohammed Jajua	MSc Livelihood and Natural Resource Management	Nigeria
11	Oumarou Mahamane Nassirou	MSc Livelihood and Natural Resource Management	Niger Republic
12	Abubakar Lawal	MSc Crops and Cropping Systems in the Drylands	Nigeria
13	Babagana Goni	MSc Crops and Cropping Systems in the Drylands	Nigeria
14.	Ismail Ibrahim Garba	MSc Crops and Cropping Systems in the Drylands	Nigeria
15	Lamin Kujabi	MSc Crops and Cropping Systems in the Drylands	Gambia
16	Ousman Sowe	MSc Crops and Cropping Systems in the Drylands	Gambia
17	Samba John	MSc Crops and Cropping Systems in the Drylands	Gambia
18	Ebou Jobe	MSc Range and Livestock Management in Drylands	Gambia
19	Adujo Atakpa	MSc Natural Resource Management and Climate Change	Nigeria

20	Ahmed Aliyu Chadi	MSc Natural Resource Management and Climate Change	Nigeria
21	Bilyaminu Ali Tofa	MSc Natural Resource Management and Climate Change	Nigeria
22	Dalibi Jamilu Haruna	MSc Natural Resource Management and Climate Change	Nigeria
23	Haruna Manu Isah	MSc Natural Resource Management and Climate Change	Nigeria
24	Hashimu Adamu Hadeja	MSc Natural Resource Management and Climate Change	Nigeria
25	Hindu Musa Karaye	MSc Natural Resource Management and Climate Change	Nigeria
26	Ja'afar Adamu Abdul Zankan	MSc Natural Resource Management and Climate Change	Nigeria
27	Kadiza Doulay SeyDou	MSc Natural Resource Mngt.	Niger Republic
28	Mahamadou Dan Abdou Idi Soge	MSc Natural Resource Management and Climate Change	Niger Republic
29	Mato Adamu	MSc Natural Resource Management and Climate Change	Nigeria
30	Nuru Moyi Isa	MSc Natural Resource Management and Climate Change	Nigeria
31	Rabiu Bala Abdulrahman	MSc Natural Resource Management and Climate Change	Nigeria
32	Salami Azeez	MSc Natural Resource Management and Climate Change	Nigeria
33	Sani Sadiq	MSc Natural Resource Management and Climate Change	Nigeria
34	Vincent Akam Ayang	MSc Natural Resource Management and Climate Change	Nigeria

